

Proof: Fluid Dynamic to Have Turbulence

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April 21, 2021

Abstract:

By using a combination of differential topology, calculus of variations, category theory and the 8-theory framework, it is possible to derive the chaotic behavior of fluid dynamics and derive the equation, which describe it. It is the same equation derived in the 8-theory to describe the time invariant acceleration and the phenomena of dark energy. The equation is a result of mixing EL equation and differential topology, and in particular, using it on Lorentz manifolds $s = (M, g)$.

Introduction

Define a Lorentz manifold

$$\mathbf{s} = (\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{g}) \quad (1)$$

Use it to assemble an Euler Lagrange Equation:

$$\begin{aligned} L &= (s, s', t) \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{L}}{\partial \mathbf{s}} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{L}}{\partial \mathbf{s}'} * \frac{\mathbf{d}}{\mathbf{d}t} &= \mathbf{0} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Develop the last equation:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Define flow of fluid as an amount of arbitrary curvature on a Lorentz manifold, marked in green.

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (4)$$

Assume it is a continuous process in time, meaning we can break it to an infinite sequence:

$$\delta g = \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots \quad (5)$$

To each we can associate an appropriate time

$$\begin{aligned} \delta g_1 &\rightarrow T_1 \\ \delta g_2 &\rightarrow T_1 + \Delta T \end{aligned}$$

That is in agreement with fluid flow, a sequence of curvature with a continuous sequence of time. Analyze the first element alone:

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_1 - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} \delta g'_1 = 0 \quad (6)$$

The first element is causing the metric to accelerate outward, so the space in which the second Element of flow is not the same as the metric in which the first element was moving in. the first Element is causing the metric to vary, and its length to vary as well, the motion cannot be put In terms of vectors Therefore, the second element itself is doing the same, it is an endless process of anymore. metric variation causing the motion to be chaotic as the metric itself varying in accordance to curvature flow. It's the same equation to describe "dark energy" in the 8- theory and the same equation that allowed us to derive the coupling constants series:

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (7)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (8)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (8.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (8.2)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \quad (8.3)$$

The setting of course is not the same framework of the Naiver – stocks analysis of motion. We needed to switch the setting by defining a functor:

$$V: Top \rightarrow Top \quad (9)$$

In order to analyze the fluid flow not in vector space but in Riemannian surface, with The Riemannian line element. Therefore, if we break down the motion of fluid to an infinite sequence, we can see why The motion of fluid cannot be put in vector form, each subset of curvature is causing An outward acceleration of the metric, and the next subset is moving in a different metric Than the first, it could revert sideways, sideways inwards, sideway outwards, and same Applies for each additional element.

End of proof
